

Supplementary Figure S1

Figure S1: Nitrogen content in queens, kings and their offspring over time. Nitrogen ratio per dry weight in offspring remained relatively flat throughout the time of the experiment, while in queens and kings, past 150 d post foundation, a nitrogen ratio increase was noticeable, as shown in inserts of Figure 3E and 3F, where pooled by pre and post 150, a significant increase was observed in queens and kings, but not in offspring. For offspring, no correlation between nitrogen ratio and time was found (Pearson Corr. = -0.03, $p = 0.86$)